

WRESTLING PREPARATION PROCESS IN SPORTS SCHOOLS

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Annotation. *In this article, a survey was conducted on the problems of maintaining a contingent of children involved in freestyle wrestling in sports schools.*

Key words: *Children, sports school, freestyle wrestling, contingent, questioning.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье проведено анкетирование по проблемам содержания контингента детей, занимающихся вольной борьбой в спортивных школах.*

Ключевые слова: *Дети, спортивная школа, вольная борьба, контингент, анкетирование.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada sport maktablarida erkin kurash bilan shug'ullanadigan bolalar kontingentini saqlash muammolari bo'yicha so'rov o'tkazildi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Bolalar, sport maktabi, erkin kurash, kontingent, so'rovnom.*

The national team of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its need for a reserve of promising young athletes in the near future require the optimization of the strategic development of innovative processes in the training of today's athletes.

A key factor in the smooth running of these processes is the willingness and unwillingness of students in sports schools to maintain the contingent. Experiments show that it is not possible to keep the number of trainees initially the same. In order to find answers to these questions, we aimed to conduct a survey in the freestyle wrestling sections of sports schools.

We developed two questionnaires:

for coaches working in freestyle wrestling sections;

for students undergoing basic training in freestyle wrestling sections;

Based on the questionnaire, we conducted an extensive survey. The survey involved a group of primary school students and their wide range of coaches. The children surveyed found that they were more interested in participating in freestyle wrestling, more interested in the art of freestyle wrestling, interacting with a coach, and being asked to work as a team in a group (22 coaches (94 trainers) participated.

All the participants expressed their desire to further improve their technical and tactical skills in freestyle wrestling and to learn different ways of wrestling. However, there was no consensus among the children on the following important questions in order to properly assess the situation. Accordingly, in part, 14.1% of children do not want to compete and participate in competitions. 14.2% of participants expressed a desire to partially participate in the competition. When these negative responses are obtained for athletes of different ages, there is also a proportionality to this amount.

Athletes aged 8-10, who are training at the sports school, also expressed their reluctance to participate in the competition. Almost all primary school-age children (95.8%) misjudge their level of ability and dream of becoming a freestyle wrestling champion.

Children in the early stages of preparation like: teamwork, recitation exercises, assignments, competition elements, and games (20.68). Pedagogical observations have shown that individual work with children aged 8-10 years is ineffective. It turned out that the peculiarity of children of this age is that they need to take into account the high level of willingness to communicate with their peers and the coach.

An analysis of responses from children who wrestled in elementary school age revealed the following:

the future of the child's wrestling depends on the personal activities of the coach;

It is known that the children who are involved in the training are liked by the coach, especially if the coach pays special attention to the children, if the children notice the coach's negligence during the whole training .

8-10 year olds showed complete confidence in their coaches. The child's impeccable attitude towards the coach, the fact that the coach in his opinion is the best and the most beloved person, and these circumstances strengthen the child's desire to communicate with the coach. It has been observed that the attachment of a young wrestler to a coach is so strong that even a short change in it leads to the idea of stopping the child's wrestling activities. Freestyle wrestlers believe that a coach should be kind to his students, regardless of age and category.

According to the results of our surveys, when we summarize the reasons for the increase or decrease in the interest of coaches and freestyle wrestlers in sports, we found the following:

Conclusion. Coaches play a key role in strengthening children's interest in freestyle wrestling in sports school. This is because the coaches' inability to fully express their children's love and confidence reduces the chances of maintaining the contingent. Surveys also revealed that it is difficult to maintain the contingent due to

teachers' dissatisfaction with the fact that children leave school too often, leaving school to the next level.

The results of the survey showed that children's participation in the practice of freestyle wrestling and the influence of factors that hinder this process, conditionally reduces the interest of children in training in the formation of a developing motivational sphere. These barriers are exacerbated by the fact that coaches do not have enough knowledge in this area.

The lack of perfect personal qualities of the coach is one of the reasons why children do not work on themselves and are not interested in their inner interests.

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